

BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS OF *LALLEMANTIA ROYLEANA* (BENTH.)
BENTH. AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN MODERN MEDICINE

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Abstract: This study presents the results of a comprehensive investigation into the chemical composition of the essential oil extracted from the aerial parts of *Lallemantia royleana* (Benth.) Benth. The qualitative and quantitative analysis of the volatile constituents was performed using gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC–MS). The plant material was collected during the active vegetative growth phase in May 2024 from the experimental plot of the Botanical Garden of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek (Tashkent city). A total of 70 volatile compounds were identified, forming the chemical profile of the essential oil.

The major constituents of the oil were β -ocimene (15.67%), citral (12.59%), nerol (12.72%), and β -citral (9.15%). These compounds exhibit significant biological activities, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects, which support the potential of *L. royleana* as a valuable source of natural bioactive substances.

The high content of monoterpenes and aldehydes in the essential oil highlights its aromatic and therapeutic properties, opening up broad prospects for its use in the pharmaceutical, food, cosmetic, and perfume industries. The findings confirm the significant potential of *L. royleana* as medicinal and technical raw material and emphasize the need for further research focused on standardization, biological evaluation, and industrial application of its essential oil.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, *Lallemantia royleana*, essential oil, GC-MS, citral, ocimene, hydrocarbons, phytotherapy, aromatic compounds.

Introduction

In recent years, the study of biologically active compounds found in medicinal plants and their application in modern medicine has become one of the most pressing topics on a global scale. The growing demand for natural remedies, the adverse side effects associated with synthetic drugs, and the increasing emphasis on environmental safety have significantly boosted interest in plant-based pharmaceuticals (World Health Organization).

The rising demand for natural agents in modern medicine and the pharmaceutical industry has enhanced the significance of many plant species, including *Lallemantia royleana* (Benth.) Benth. (Mahmood S. et al., 2013; Ghannadi A. et al., 2015; Bozorgi M., Vazirian M., 2016; Al-Snafi A.E., 2019; Sardarodiyani M. et al., 2019; Saleem A. et al., 2022).

The seeds of *L. royleana* have been identified as promising for medical use due to their healing and antioxidant properties, high total phenolic content, and their effectiveness in reducing cholesterol and triglyceride levels in blood serum (Mahmood S. et al., 2013; Bozorgi M., Vazirian M., 2016; Sardarodiyani M. et al., 2019; Saleem A. et al., 2022; Ghannadi A. et al., 2015).

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The seeds of *L. royleana* contain 25.60% protein, 18.27% fat, 1.29% fiber, as well as alkaloids, anthraquinones, flavonoids, glycosides, phlobatannins, volatile oils, mixed fatty acids, and terpenoids. These compounds have demonstrated a wide range of pharmacological effects, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidepressant, anxiolytic, sedative, antiemetic, hypolipidemic, and protective activities. Some studies suggest that these compounds could be useful in the treatment of skin diseases (Al-Snafi A.E., 2019; Massey S. et al., 2022; Saleem A. et al., 2022).

Traditionally, *L. royleana* seeds have been used in folk medicine for the treatment of various conditions, particularly digestive disorders, respiratory inflammations, and skin diseases (Saleem A. et al., 2022). In recent years, extracts and bioactive components derived from this plant have increasingly been incorporated into modern pharmaceutical formulations, further underscoring its medical relevance (Mahmood S. et al., 2013; Atabaki R., Hassanpour-Ezatti M., 2014).

A chemical analysis of essential oil obtained from the aerial parts of *Lallemantia royleana* (Benth. in Wall.) Benth., cultivated in Isfahan province, Iran, using gas chromatography (GC) and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS), revealed 46 components. The major constituents were identified as verbenone (16.4%), trans-carveol (9.8%), and β -cubebene (8.9%) (Ghannadi A., Zolfaghari B., 2003). Furthermore, literature analysis indicates that the essential oil composition of the vegetative organs of *L. royleana* remains poorly studied.

However, scientific interest in this plant has grown in recent years, especially due to the pharmacological potential of its volatile compounds (essential oils).

This article presents an analysis of the chemical composition of the biologically active compounds in *L. royleana*, their pharmacological mechanisms of action, and directions for their application in modern medicine. The potential for practical implementation of these findings is also discussed based on current scientific literature.

Materials and Methods

Plant material collection and identification

The object of this study is *Lallemantia royleana* (Benth.) Benth., a medicinal and essential oil-bearing plant belonging to the Lamiaceae family, widely cultivated in various regions of the world. It is commonly known as "Balangu" in Iran, "Tukh Malanga" in Pakistan, and "Mallachoy" in Uzbekistan. Plant samples were collected during the juvenile stage in May 2024 from the experimental plot of the Botanical Garden, Faculty of Biology and Ecology, National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek (Tashkent). The species was identified by Professor Zafar Muhammad, from Quaid-i-Azam University. Voucher specimens were deposited in the Department of Botany and Genetics, National University of Uzbekistan.

Essential oil extraction

A total of 266 grams of fresh aerial parts of the plant were crushed and subjected to hydro-distillation for 5 hours using a Clevenger-type apparatus. The essential oil obtained was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and stored in sealed amber vials at +4 °C in a dark environment until further analysis.

GC-MS analysis method

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was performed using an Agilent 7890B GC system coupled with a 5977A mass selective detector. The system was equipped with a DB-5MS capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., film thickness 0.25 μ m). Injection volume was 1.0 μ L in split mode (split ratio 1:50), with helium as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The oven temperature program was as follows: initial temperature of 50 °C (held for 2 minutes), increased at a rate of 5 °C/min to 250 °C, and held for 39 minutes.

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Mass spectrometry was performed in electron ionization (EI) mode at 70 eV with a scan range of 40 to 550 m/z. Compounds were identified by comparing their mass spectra and retention indices with data from the NIST08.L, W9N11.L, and W8N05ST.L spectral libraries. The relative percentage of each component was calculated based on peak area normalization without applying correction factors.

Results

GC-MS analysis revealed a total of 70 compounds, primarily corresponding to terpenes and hydrocarbons. The major constituents identified in the essential oil included α -terpinene, limonene, β -phellandrene, ocimene, p-cymene, geraniol, citral, nerol, pinocarvone, germacrene-D, and farnesol. The most abundant components were β -ocimene (15.67%), nerol (12.72%), citral (12.59%), pinocarvone (9.08%), and germacrene-D (5.69%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Chemical constituents of *L. royleana* essential oil identified by GC-MS

No	Retention Time (min)	Compound Name	CAS Number	Relative Abundance (%)	Identification Quality
1	2.462	α -Terpinene	99-86-5	0.15	97
2	2.688	Limonene	138-86-3	0.38	98
3	2.785	β -Phellandrene	555-10-2	0.32	95
4	3.108	β -Ocimene	6874-10-8	15.67	97
5	3.218	γ -Terpinene	99-85-4	0.49	96
6	3.309	β -Ocimene Y	3779-61-1	2.95	96
7	3.509	p-Cymene	99-87-6	0.21	95
8	3.736	α -Terpinene	99-86-5	0.06	95
9	3.768	Isoamyl-2-methyl butyrate	27625-35-0	0.10	58
10	4.609	6-Methyl-5-hepten-2-one	110-93-0	0.78	95
11	5.017	Camphene	79-92-5	0.08	78
12	5.541	Neo-allo-ocimene	673-84-7	0.27	98
13	5.851	Cyclooctene	61233-78-1	0.09	72
14	5.993	Nonanal	124-19-6	0.06	90
15	7.035	1-Octen-3-ol	3391-86-4	0.07	53
16	7.462	γ -Terpinene	99-85-4	0.25	95
17	7.604	Isopentyl hexanoate	2198-61-0	0.04	64
18	8.503	Copaene	947-59-1	0.07	97
19	8.943	1-Hexene, 4,5-dimethyl	16106-59-5	0.19	53
20	9.034	Pinanone	15358-88-0	1.83	95
21	9.318	Cyclohexaneacetaldehyde	3991-38-6	0.08	50
22	9.473	Pinocarvone	30460-92-5	9.08	91
23	9.862	Bicyclohept-2-en-4-ol acetate	998166-34-6	5.35	89
24	10.767	γ -Terpinene	99-85-4	1.73	83
25	11.071	Myrtenal	564-94-3	1.35	98
26	11.705	trans-Pinocarveol	547-61-5	1.05	70

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27	12.359	cis-p-Mentha-2,8-dien-1-ol	3886-78-0	0.07	70
28	12.501	p-Mentha-1,3,8-triene	18368-95-1	0.18	74
29	12.701	Tetracyclodecane	998041-92-9	0.32	68
30	12.857	Citral	106-26-3	9.15	96
31	13.277	3-Carene	13466-78-9	0.22	83
32	13.665	Germacrene-D	23986-74-5	5.69	98
33	13.995	Camphene	79-92-5	0.87	90
34	14.215	Citral	5392-40-5	12.59	97
35	14.836	Nerol	106-25-2	12.72	91
36	15.043	β -Citronellol	106-22-9	0.30	96
37	15.159	Bicycloheptane	79-92-5	0.05	46
38	15.237	Myrtenol	515-00-4	0.64	81
39	15.703	Nerol	106-25-2	3.42	89
40	15.890	(E)-1-Iodo-6-(4-isopropenyl-1-cyclohexenyl)-3-methyl-3-hexene	998573-46-0	0.07	53
41	16.000	trans-1,2-Dihydroperillaldehyde	998072-24-6	0.09	58
42	16.123	2,6-Dimethyl-1,3,5,7-octatetraene, E,E-	460-01-5	0.06	86
43	16.460	Artemisia triene	18383-70-5	0.15	64
44	16.964	Nerol	106-25-2	7.00	91
45	17.449	Tetracyclodecane	1000185-58-7	0.06	59
46	18.607	α -Pinene	80-56-8	0.13	70
47	19.118	Geranyl acetate	105-87-3	0.04	74
48	20.321	Nonadecane	629-92-5	0.20	96
49	20.503	1,3,8-P-Menthatriene	18368-95-1	0.13	46
50	20.574	1(7),3,8-O-Menthatriene	000000-00-0	0.05	46
51	21.654	p-Menthatriene	18368-95-1	0.05	49
52	21.803	Bicyclo[4.2.0]oct-1-ene	998041-92-1	0.33	72
53	22.948	Fumaric acid, myrtenyl pentyl ester	998518-22-2	0.15	59
54	23.071	Camphene	79-92-5	0.07	52
55	23.181	3-Hexen-1-ol, benzoate	25152-85-6	0.21	90
56	24.423	Nerol	106-25-2	0.36	87
57	24.901	1-Octadecanesulphonyl chloride	998590-84-2	0.32	70

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58	25.063	γ -Cadinene	39029-41-9	0.08	50
59	25.716	δ -Cadinene	483-76-1	0.19	86
60	27.760	Farnesol	4602-84-0	0.06	72
61	29.145	Tricosane	638-67-5	0.19	93
62	30.070	Artemisia triene	18383-70-5	0.08	46
63	31.868	2-Thiophen-2-yl-1H-pyrrole	998064-45-6	0.03	72
64	33.110	Cyclotetradecane	295-17-0	0.31	89
65	33.505	Ethanol, 2-(3,3-dimethylcyclohexylidene)-, (Z)	26532-23-0	0.09	81
66	33.996	(2E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecene	14237-73-1	0.18	50
67	34.294	3-Oxatetracyclo[5.3.1.0(2,4).0(6,8)]undec-9-ene	63896-19-5	0.06	45
68	35.005	Pentafluoropropionic acid, octadecyl ester	999040-90-3	0.04	42
69	36.816	Octatetracontane, 1-iodo	40710-70-1	0.21	90
70	38.776	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z) (Oleic acid)	112-80-1	0.09	64

The main components of the essential oil consist of monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and aldehydes (Table 2).

Table 2. Main chemical groups in the essential oil of *L. royleana*

Chemical Group	Content (%)	Major Compounds
Monoterpenes	40–45%	Limonene, γ -Terpinene, α -Terpinene, β -Phellandrene
Sesquiterpenes	10–15%	Germacrene-D, Copaene, Farnesol
Aldehydes	20–25%	Citral, Nonanal
Alcohols	15–20%	Nerol, Myrtenol, trans-Pinocarveol

Discussion

A total of 70 chemical components were identified in the essential oil of *Lallemantia royleana*. Among these, the dominant compounds in the mixture are as follows:

Citral (combined cis and trans isomers): 21.74% – Exhibits strong antibacterial and antifungal activity. Due to its citrus aroma, it is widely used in perfumery and cosmetic formulations. Additionally, it possesses anti-inflammatory and antiseptic properties [11].

Nerol: 19.72% – Characterized by a mild floral scent, this compound has calming and antidepressant effects. It is commonly used in cosmetics for its soothing and antiseptic action on the skin [12].

β -Ocimene: 15.67% – Demonstrates anti-inflammatory and insecticidal properties. In aromatherapy, it is utilized to relieve stress and tension. It also plays a significant role in the plant's natural defense system [13].

Secondary components present in the mixture include:

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Pinocarvone: 9.08% – Exhibits antibacterial and antifungal properties. Widely used in the perfume industry and has potential application as a natural pesticide [14].

Germacrene-D: 5.69% – Possesses antimicrobial and insecticidal activities. It strengthens the natural defense mechanisms of plants and is also used in perfumery [15].

The GC-MS analysis of *Lallemantia royleana* essential oil revealed a complex mixture of volatile compounds, with a noticeable presence of terpenes such as cis-Ocimene, dl-Limonene, β -Phellandrene, γ -Terpinene, and p-Cymene. High-quality identification scores for most of the detected compounds confirm the reliability of the results. This essential oil contains a wide array of aromatic compounds commonly found in plants and essential oils.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the high concentrations of Citral, Nerol, and Ocimene in the essential oil suggest its suitability for use in perfumery and aromatherapy products. Compounds such as Pinocarvone and Germacrene-D exhibit notable antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, making them promising candidates for therapeutic applications. Additionally, Limonene, Ocimene, and other terpenoids are well known for their antibacterial and antioxidant effects.

Citral, with its lemon-like aroma, is widely utilized as a flavoring agent in the food and beverage industries. The oil is predominantly composed of monoterpenes (e.g., Ocimene, Citral, Nerol), which contribute citrusy, floral, and sweet aromatic notes. Sesquiterpenes like Germacrene-D add woody and earthy tones to the oil's scent profile.

The primary component identified was cis-Ocimene, with the highest relative abundance of 15.67%. Other key compounds include dl-Limonene, β -Phellandrene, γ -Terpinene, and p-Cymene, which are recognized for their aromatic and potential therapeutic properties. Several peaks in the chromatogram correspond to unidentified compounds, indicating the need for further analysis or updates to spectral libraries for more accurate identification.

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